

PRIORITIES OF EDUCATIONAL WORK WITH MEDICAL STUDENTS

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The article deals with ways to improve the organization of forms of educational work in a higher educational medical institution. The paper analyzes the effectiveness of involving students in socially useful activities, volunteering, which will reveal the personal potential of a young person, feel their belonging to society, as well as create favorable conditions for personal and professional development, self-identification. Consequently, in the educational process of higher education institutions, in particular medical, the use of volunteering, involvement in public life is an indispensable part of the process of training future doctors.

Keywords: educational process, educational work, volunteering, medical students.

Modern higher education institutions (HEIs) should not only provide the necessary knowledge and practical professional skills, but also educate a responsible citizen of their state as an integrated and comprehensively developed person who can think freely and self-organize in modern conditions [2]. When determining the content and organization of forms of educational work in higher education institutions, it is necessary to create a "portrait" of student youth, which will allow to determine the characteristics of each, to understand why some forms and methods have a positive result on some representatives of student youth and almost no results for others. It is well-known that the student age is primarily marked by the gaining of a certain autonomy and skills of future professional career. However, this is not the only point that is common for the student age. The entrancing to the HEI and choosing a specialty is already a self-identifying process. In accordance to the literature, in this age period, the individual is undergoing a crisis of "identity", the formation of the "core" of identity, the development of which is affected by the engagement of a young person in the different social establishments of the community and the cognizance of their belonging to them. At this age, a human's orientations, their plans for life, the decision-making abilities and responsibility for them, the acceptance of social roles and the forming of relevant behaviour patterns are also determined [1, 3].

According to national investigators, the formation of responsibility is supported by the awareness of their engagement in the community, the processes in it, respectively, a young person is aware that they are in charge of the transformations taking place in their surrounding, the society to which they are part of [5]. It is common knowledge that students are very active members of public life, under the condition of organizing such life. The social environment during this period is conducive to being active, as the individual is surrounded by the same young people, there is time that allows you to use your personal capacities and potential, and also to balance both professional and social advancement. The combination of valuable and occupational is the implementation of community-oriented training, where young people apply the acquired professional knowledge to serve the community and deal

with their issues. Society-oriented education is a world-known innovational educational approach that is aimed to increase the civil engagement of students and lecturers, as well as creating beneficial social transformations in the education process. This method facilitates the team work improvement, leadership, critical thinking, and ensures the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals, in addition to poverty and famine eradication, high-quality education, strong health, gender equality, dignified work, responsible consumption, etc. Community-based learning is innovative, departing from the tradition of individual work and leads to a team-based one. It is about communication, not only inside the establishment itself, but also with the community. This improves the understanding and resolving of challenges in those fields where there is a necessity. It is not that easy to inspire students to implement projects because of lack of time. Students undertake projects that are truly meaningful to them. Accordingly, the subject of educational work is the engagement of students in community activities, organization of different kinds of activities, considering the needs of the youth. Nowadays, the educational work of HEIs contains the implementation of volunteering activities, involvement of students in solving socially urgent cases, which enables to disclose the individual potential of young people, to feel their belonging to society, their value in dealing with such problems. Scientists consider that engaging young people in solving social problems of society through socially useful activities satisfies such a need as belonging and actualization [6, 7].

Students of Bukovinian State Medical University are also deeply engaged in a variety of volunteer activities. In particularly, they actively served at the Regional Center of Disease Control and Prophylaxis during the Covid pandemic, where, in cooperation with epidemiologists, future doctors monitored infected patients, informed the locals about vaccination against COVID-19, informed about the nearest vaccination stations and vaccination centers, emphasizing that the procedure is completely safe and free of charge. The students worked in their leisure time to help people to stay healthy and to make medicine high-quality and available.

The war in our country makes corrections in the lifestyle of all of us - we have to live, work and take care of each other in unfamiliar conditions. The future doctors were one of the first who joined the initiative of making camouflage nets for the needs of the defenders of Ukraine, the procurement of ammunition and medications for the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Moreover, students of our university work at humanitarian aid warehouses, where they help in unloading and sorting medicines.

According to scientists, the volunteering sector is one of the most efficient ways of cooperation with various categories of people, it is an endless source of civic education, allows students to express themselves in the community service [8]. "Love and help" is the credo of all those who cannot stay away from people who need support and help, care and kindness. These feelings, which cannot be raised by any rules and laws, are inherent in volunteers who are guided by the next principles in their work: voluntariness, which provides that persons involved in volunteer activities have made this choice themselves and voluntarily and do not need legal enforcement for this; the principle of gratuitousness means that volunteer assistance provided by volunteers or a volunteer organization is unpaid, i.e. volunteers or volunteer organizations do not receive any financial benefit for the services provided or work performed, except for moral satisfaction; the principle of unselfishness means the possibility to bring joy and benefit to people without expecting personal benefits in return; the principle of non-profitability means that volunteers and volunteer organizations do not receive any income while carrying out their missions and functions, and their activities are declared non-profit.

One of the most perspective fields of medical volunteering is participation in the work of palliative and hospice services. The mission of the service is to provide palliative care to patients and their families who are faced with a serious, in many cases terminal disease. The work at the hospice is the best school for training the moral qualities of future junior healthcare professionals and doctors, which gives students the opportunity to reconsider life values, reflect on the philosophical issues of human existence, teaches them to appreciate human dignity, develops high moral human qualities - compassion, unselfishness, respect for the person, care and mercy. The arrangement of such work definitely needs prepared specialists who have the appropriate skills. By implementing a new conceptual model of nurses' training, we provide practical sessions

in the Hospice in the disciplines "Basics of Nursing" and "Nursing Care", "Nursing in gerontology, geriatrics and palliative care". In addition, for many years, students of III-IV years of study have been undergoing summer practice at the hospice and provide all necessary assistance to medical staff in taking care of severely ill patients. While organizing the work of students, first of all, we highlight the significance of interpersonal communication with patients and their relatives. By applying the elements of care for critically ill patients, communicating with them, students have the possibility of self-realization, self-development as a future specialist and citizen.

Therefore, the main goal of educational work with students is to create favorable environment for individual and professional development, self-identification, determination of one's own place in society, values, and acceptance of socially approved forms of behavior. The content, forms and methods of socially-oriented learning are exactly corresponding to these tasks. So, the work on the organization and integration of forms of socially-oriented education in the learning process of HEIs is an incredibly promising direction.

References

1. Zlyvko V. L. Profesiina identychnist ta osobystist pedahoha. Kyiv, 2014; 131.
2. Kolesnyk Yu. M., Nerianov Yu.M., Kompaniets V.M. Yakist pidhotovky fakhivtstv – holovna skladova Bolonskoho protsesu. Medychna osvita, 2011; 2: 71–74.
3. Kopets L. V. Psykholohiia osobystosti: navch. posib. dlia stud. vyshch. navch. zakl. Kyiv: Vyd. dim «Kyievo–Mohylianska akademiia», 2017; 460.
4. Maksymenko S. D., Filonenko M.M. Pedahohika vyshchoi medychnoi osvity. Kyiv: Tsentri uchbovoi literatury, 2014; 109–116.
5. Orban-Lembryk L. E. Sotsialna psykholohiia. Navch. posibnyk. Kyiv: Akademvydav, 2013; 568.
6. Safonova N. Tvorchyi pedahoh – fundator formuvannia tvorchoi osobystosti. Ridna shkola, 2017; 2: 10–11.
7. Bashkir O. I. Modern formats of professional development of educational community. Innovative solutions in modern science, 2018; 3 (22):116-128.
8. Maslow A. H. A Theory of Human Motivation. URL: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi:10.1.1.318.2317&rep=rep1&type=pdf> (дата звернення 27.05.2020 p.)